

New Tetracylic Triterpenes of *Fomes Senex**

S. RANGASWAMI

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

I deem it a great honour and privilege to be asked to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture and I thank the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for having elected me to this honour. The Acharya was unique in several ways. He was the earliest in India to train young Indian students in chemical research. He inspired them not only in chemistry but also indirectly by the personal life he lived, that of a great *Rishi*. He was also the earliest to bring the fruits of chemistry to the citizens of the country and he was the prime force behind what is perhaps the oldest chemical industry in India, the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works. I had the privilege of seeing him at close quarters in 1931 when he came to the Chemistry Department of the Madras Presidency College, to see my teacher Prof. B. B. Dey, one of the old generation of chemical researchers of our country, whom he loved very much. Frail in frame and dressed in archaic fashion, we realised that here was an extraordinary man, and considered it a great piece of luck when he took time to exchange a few words with us, his chemical grand-students. The Acharya was indeed one of the noblest sons of India, an institution by himself.

I have chosen to speak to-day on a topic on which we at the Delhi University Chemistry Department have been engaged for some years now. Natural products chemists from sub-tropical and cold countries have occasionally remarked that they envy their counterparts in tropical countries because the latter do not have the problem of finding problems; our chemistry literally grows on our trees, they say. My topic today deals with chemistry that grows not on living trees but on dead trees.

Fungi are beneficial to man in many ways and detrimental in certain other ways. As illustrations of the former one may mention their use in alcoholic fermentation and in the synthesis of citric acid, gallic acid, kojic acid and medicinal products like antibiotics and steroid hormones. On the other hand some fungal species are responsible for certain diseases of man generally termed mycoses. Food spoilage, which includes food poisoning is an extremely harmful activity of fungi. Many species of mushrooms or toad-stools are very poisonous if eaten directly and result in violent illness and even death. On the other hand there are also many edible mushrooms. Many fungi are employed in the processing of certain food products like cheese. Wood-rotting fungi, but for a few exceptions, belong to the group of Basidiomycetes; among these the following families are important: Agaricaceae, Hydnaceae, Polyporaceae and Thelephoraceae. On the one hand they cause great economic loss by damaging and destroying timber and lumber on a

large scale, but on the other hand they are very useful in that they eat away the dead plants which would otherwise lie indefinitely on the forest ground and accumulate and thus would eventually inhibit the growth of new plants.

Fungi which inhabit wood may be broadly divided into three groups depending upon the nature of their development in and on the wood and the type of changes or deterioration for which they are responsible. They are the wood-destroying or wood-rotting fungi, the wood-staining fungi and the moulds; of these the first group is by far the most important economically. The development of the decay-producing fungi depends upon a number of factors; these are a supply of suitable food, a sufficient degree of moisture, at least a small amount of air and a favourable temperature. Deficiency in any one of these requirements will inhibit the growth of the fungus. The fungus obtains its food from the wood by breaking down the constituents of the cell walls and transforming them into food by means of enzymes that it secretes. The two principal types of compounds entering into the composition of wood cells are cellulose and lignin, and the actual effect of fungal attack will depend upon which substance is removed. In general the cellulose components of wood are light in colour, soft but tough and have great affinity for water, whereas the lignin components are dark, hard and brittle and have little affinity for water. Therefore wood that has been acted upon by a lignin dissolving fungus contains a relatively high remainder of cellulose and will be whiter in comparison with normal wood. It will, in addition, be soft and spongy in texture. A decay of this sort is known as "white-rot". Wood from which the cellulose compounds have been removed will be darker than normal wood and will be dry and brittle. A decay of this sort is known as "brown rot". If both cellulose and lignin have been removed from the wood, as happens in some cases, a hole or hollow results. A decay of this type is termed "pocket-rot".

The heart wood of trees is commonly regarded as more durable than the sap wood. But this statement will apply only to trees which have already been converted into lumber. In the case of living trees the sap wood is almost immune to decay fungi, unless it is exposed by the creation of a wound of some sort, and even then the decay is strictly localised. The decays that infest living trees are, with this exception, always decays of the heart wood and are called "heart-rots". On the other hand in dead or down timber and in lumber cut from living trees the sap wood may undergo extensive decay. Decay of the sap wood is usually

* Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture for 1973 delivered on December 23, 1974 before the Annual Convention of Chemists at the Madurai University.

called "sap-rot" and is ordinarily carried on by species of fungi different from those that decay the heart woods.

The biochemical activities of the lower fungi commonly known as moulds have been intensively studied and a great deal of information is now available about the metabolism of species belonging to certain genera like *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium*. On the other hand comparatively little attention has been given to the metabolic activities of the Basidiomycetes which grow on wood. Since decay in wood and its prevention are matters of great economic importance, the decomposition of wood has been studied in some detail, but comparatively little is known about the chemistry of substances elaborated by the fungi which decompose them.

The metabolites of fungi have been found to belong to diverse chemical groups like aliphatic compounds, aromatic compounds, carbohydrates, polyenes, polyacetylenes, quinones of various types, nitrogen-containing compounds, like amines, amino acids, peptides and nitrogen heterocyclics, and steroids and terpenoids. In each group both very simple and very complex compounds have been found. Some examples of fungal compounds which are unique on account of their elemental composition and/or chemical structure are agrocybin from *Agrocybe dura*, drosophilin-A from *Drosophila substrata* (and its methyl ether isolated at Delhi from *Fomes fastuosus*), fomentaric acid from *Fomes fomentarius*, also studied at Delhi, muscarufin from *Amanita muscaria*, thelephoric acid from many species of *Thelephora*, gliotoxin from *Gliocladium fimbriatum* and geodoxin from *Aspergillus terreus*. The respective structures are shown in the same order in Chart I.

Fomes species, also frequently referred to as *Polyporus* species even by fungal taxonomists, appear to be the commonest to grow in the forests of the lower reaches of the Himalayas. Species collected from places separated by as much as 200 to 400 miles were identified as *Fomes* species. Since they were collected more or less from comparable altitudes, 8000 to 12000 feet above sea level, altitude seems to have a greater influence on the nature of the genera. Taking all factors into account, it may be said that in our study the most interesting results have emerged from *Fomes senex*. This fungus collected by one of our research students (now Dr.) A. K. Batta from the Dehra Dun region in the Himalayas is shown in Plate 1.

Plate 1 *Fomes senex*

Chart I

The petroleum ether extract of the fungus contained three neutral components, whose proportions varied in batches of the fungus collected in different years, and in addition two acidic components. The subsequent ether extract contained a new acid component as the major constituent; this was named senexdiolic acid in the light of knowledge gained from its detailed studies described in the sequel. The neutral components of the petroleum ether extract were found to be also new and to be related to senexdiolic acid as a result of detailed studies and these are described later.

The two acids present in the petroleum ether extract were found to be unsaturated and to be interrelated as alcohol and ketone. Mild oxidation of the former gave the latter, from which it was got back on mild reduction with sodium borohydride. A detailed study by the preparation of derivatives like the ester and acetate, complete reduction to the corresponding diol and dehydrogenation to a heteroannular diene and their characterisation by u. v., n. m. r. and mass spectra resulted in their identification as trametenolic acid B (I) and pinicolic acid A (II), both of which are already known in the literature (see Chart II).

Structure of senexdiolic acid: The substance had the molecular formula $C_{30}H_{48}O_4$ and answered the Liebermann-Burchard colour reaction. These and the n. m. r. spectra of the derivatives showed that it was a tetracyclic triterpene. It contained one carboxyl group as evidenced by the formation of a mono methyl ester and two hydroxy groups both of which could be easily acetylated and oxidised with CrO_3 to keto groups. For reasons that will become obvious later, the latter reaction had to be carried out on the methyl ester. The tetranitromethane test was positive.

The 24 : 25 Double bond and C_{22} -OH: The molecular formula and the tetracyclic nature of the compound indicated the presence of two double bonds. Of these one was easily reducible under catalytic conditions while the other was resistant. The location of the former at the 24 : 25 position in the side chain followed from the observation that m/e 69 was the

base-peak in the mass spectrum; this value corresponds to the fragment *a* (see Chart II). This location got confirmation from the formation of acetone on ozonolysis or by the action of osmium tetroxide followed by sodium metaperiodate. The n. m. r. spectrum of the diketo methyl ester gave evidence for the presence of a $-CO-CH_2-CH=C$ moiety, thereby locating one of the oxygen functions at C_{22} . This received support from the mass spectrum of methyl senexdiolate in which the peak at m/e 99 can be attributed to fragment *b*. The location of the hydroxyl at C_{22} and a double bond at 24 : 25 led to the following interesting result; treatment of senexdiolic acid with mineral acid gave rise to a new isomeric compound in which both the hydroxyl and double bond had vanished, evidently due to mutual interaction leading to the formation of an oxide ring. Similar treatment of 24-dihydro-senexdiolic acid produced no change. The n. m. r. spectrum of the isomer showed that the ring oxygen had two gem-methyl groups α to it. The ring should therefore be a tetrahydrofuran. This was supported by i. r. absorptions at ~ 1135 and ~ 885 cm^{-1} in this compound and in the closely related compound oxido-senexone described later. This ring moiety appeared as the fragment *c* in the mass spectrum. Compounds with this structural feature are referred to as oxido compounds in this article. The above results are depicted in Chart III.

The C_3 -OH and COOH: When the acid isomerised senexdiolic acid which may be called oxido-senexolic acid was subjected to CrO_3 oxidation, the second OH group became a ketone but simultaneous decarboxylation was observed (see Chart IV). It is shown later that this hydroxyl is at C_3 , and hence it follows that the $-COOH$ should be C_{30} or C_{31} . The positive Zimmermann colour reaction and n. m. r. and mass spectra of the nor-ketone gave full support to this structure.

The i. r. spectrum of the methyl ester of senexdiolic acid exhibited a strong absorption at 1245 cm^{-1} indicating the equatorial configuration of the $COOCH_3$ group. Had it been axial it would have shown absorptions at 1155 (s), 1190 (m) and 1230 (w) cm^{-1} . In another approach to this question the $COOMe$ group was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to CH_2OH which was then acetylated to $-CH_2OAc$. The n. m. r. signal of the methylene protons of this CH_2OAc appeared as an AB quartet centered at δ 3.82 ppm with a J value of 10 Hz. This again showed that the

-CH₂OAc group which corresponds to the original COOMe group was in equatorial and not axial configuration. Had the CH₂OAc been axial the methylene protons would have given an AB quartet centered at $\delta \sim 4.2$ ppm with a J value of ~ 19 Hz. Hence the carboxyl group in senexdiolic acid represents C₃₀ and not C₃₁.

Chart IV

The 8 : 9 double bond : The double bond resistant to catalytic hydrogenation was shown by i. r. to be tetrasubstituted. By analogy with other naturally occurring compounds it should be at 8 : 9. The best proof for this location comes from the fact that compounds having this double bond get oxidised by selenium dioxide to the 7 : 8, 9 : 11-diene, which is recognisable by typical absorption maxima and log ϵ values. These values are also useful in providing information about the stereo chemistry at C₁₃ and C₁₄ and distinguish between lanostane derivatives which have 13 β and 14 α methyl configurations and euphane derivatives which have the reverse stereochemistry at these positions. In the case of senexdiolic acid and its derivatives, oxidation with selenium dioxide gave the 7:8, 9:11-diene which had absorption maxima at 236, 242 and 252 nm with log ϵ values 4.13, 4.16 and 4.11 respectively. The location of the tetra-substituted and resistant double bond of senexdiolic acid was thus confirmed as 8 : 9 and the compound itself could be assigned to the lanostane series.

Chart V

Correlation with lanostenol Senexdiolic acid having thus been shown to be a lanostane derivative the logical next step was to correlate it with a lanostane derivative of known structure. An obvious choice was trametenolic acid B which, as mentioned earlier, occurs in the same fungus. Senexdiolic acid and trametenolic acid B resemble each other in some respects and differ in others. They are similar in having the lanostane skeleton, double bonds at 8 : 9 and 24 : 25 and hydroxyl at 3. Since the 24 : 25 double bond is easily reduced under catalytic conditions in both cases, the 24 dihydro compounds were selected as convenient starting points. Senexdiolic acid and trametenolic acid differ in the

number and position of oxidised centres. Thus C₃₀ exists as COOH in the former and CH₃ in the latter, while C₂₁ exists as COOH in the latter and as CH₃ in the former. To enable a comparison both C₃₀ and C₂₁ should be transformed to the same stage of oxidation in both compounds. Complete reduction to the CH₃ stage was attempted as being the most convenient. Employing the following sequence of

reactions :- $\text{COOH} \xrightarrow[\text{LAH}]{\text{CH}_2\text{N}_2} \text{-COOMe} \xrightarrow[\text{LAH}]{\text{TsCl}} \text{-CH}_2\text{OH}$ $\rightarrow \text{-CH}_2\text{OTs} \rightarrow \text{-CH}_3$, both C₃₀ and C₂₁ were obtained in the form of CH₃ in both compounds. A further difference between the two acids is that C₂₂ exists as CHOH in senexdiolic acid and as CH₂ in trametenolic acid. Comparability was facilitated by the reduction of CHOH in the former acid to CH₂, even during the above sequence of reactions, in the following

manner : $\text{CHOH} \xrightarrow[\text{LAH}]{\text{TsCl}} \text{CHOTs} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2$. As is to be expected, the final reduction stage yielded mixtures in both series, but one product derived from each series proved completely identical between themselves according to m. p., m. m. p., t. l. c. and i. r. spectrum. Elemental composition and physical properties showed that it was 3 β -hydroxy-lanost-8-ene (see Chart V). Evidently the 3-OH had been partly regenerated while the primary hydroxyls at 30 or 21 and the secondary hydroxyl at 22 had been completely deoxygenated. This correlation confirmed the earlier conclusions regarding the structure of senexdiolic acid and also furnished definite proof for the 3 β -hydroxyl in it. The compound can therefore be formulated as 3 β , 22-dihydroxy-lanost-8, 24-dien-30-oic acid.

Chart VI

Structure of the neutral compounds : The oxido nor-ketone mentioned earlier was found to be identical according to m. p., mixed m. p., t. l. c., i. r. with one of the neutral components of the petroleum ether extract which has therefore been given the name oxidosenexone. Its structure is as represented in chart VI. The same compound was found to result by acid treatment of another neutral component in the petroleum ether extract which possessed a hydroxyl group, a keto group, an easily reducible and a resistant double bond and answered Zimmermann colour test. The latter compound should, therefore, have the structure shown and has been called senexonol (see Chart VI.) Mild

CrO₃ oxidation of senexonol gave rise to the third neutral component of the petroleum ether extract which has two keto functions and two double bonds. It should therefore have the structure shown in Chart VII and has been called senexdione.

The nor compounds were unaffected by refluxing with alcoholic KOH. According to Djerassi et al. this would indicate that the C₄-CH₃ group is having the stable equatorial (α) configuration. This conclusion is incorporated in the structures shown in Chart VII

Chart VII

The discovery of the co-occurrence of trametenolic acid B, pinicolic acid A, senexdiolic acid, senexonol, senexdione and oxidosenexone in one and the same source is of great biogenetic significance in connection with the origin of sterols. It was established beyond doubt nearly 20 years ago that the first C₃₀ terpene compound to be biosynthesised is the aliphatic compound squalene, and that this yields the tetracyclic trimethylsterol lanosterol (I, Chart VIII) through epoxidation at a terminal double bond, then attack of oxide ring by proton and simultaneous concerted ring closure at a number of points. It was also established that lanosterol which is a C₃₀ compound is the precursor of cholesterol (II) which is a C₂₇ compound, and that the change involves loss, one after another, of three methyl groups, the two geminal ones at position 4 and the one at 14, each carbon being converted to carbon dioxide quantitatively. Nothing definite was known about the sequence of removal of these three methyls nor was the mechanism of their loss clearly understood. The isolation of 4-methylsterols, 14-methylsterols, 4,4-dimethylsterols and 4, 14-dimethylsterols has led to considerable speculation about the order in which the extra methyl groups are removed

from lanosterol in its passage to cholesterol. It was believed earlier that the methyl at 14 is removed first and then those at 4. But now there is reason to believe that the methyls at 4 can also be the first to be lost. Some recent labelled experiments carried out in other laboratories have thrown much light on which of the two methyl groups at position 4 is the first to be removed, on an intermediate oxidised stage prior to final elimination, and the fate of the remaining methyl prior to its removal in its turn. Under the action of rat liver enzymes 4,4-dimethyl-cholestanol (I, Chart IX) first gives rise to the 4 α -hydroxymethyl-4 β -methylsterol

Chart VIII

Chart IX

Chart X

(II), and after the α -carbon is removed, the residual 4β -methyl is epimerised to 4α -methyl (III), then gets oxidised to 4α -hydroxymethyl and is finally lost yielding cholestanol (IV). In the plant kingdom when cycloartanol (I, Chart X) is converted into nor-cycloartanol (II) by *Polypodium vulgare*, it is the 4α -methyl that is lost, but then the residual 4β -methyl epimerises to 4α and this is the stereochemistry at 4 that is found in norcycloartanol. In like manner when 24-methylenecycloartanol (III) loses one methyl at the 4-position to become cycloeucalenol (IV) in the banana peel, it is the 4α -methyl group that is removed, but again the residual 4β -methyl epimerises to 4α and this is the stereochemistry found in cycloeucalenol. In senexdiolic acid, the oxidised carbon at position 4 is the α -carbon and not the β -carbon, and in this it resembles

4α -hydroxymethyl- 4β -methylcholestanol. In the nor compounds senexonol, senexdione and oxidosenexone, all of which are evidently derived from senexdiolic acid in the plant, the residual carbon atom at 4, which was originally β in senexdiolic acid, has epimerised to 4α and this is similar to what has been mentioned above as taking place in the demethylation of cycloartanol and 24-methylene-cycloartanol. Thus the results of our investigations on *Fomes senex* are parallel to those that have been obtained by the use of labelled experiments, and in this respect constitute a modest contribution to our understanding of the biogenesis of sterols.

I wish to thank Dr. A. K. Batta, a former student of mine, for much of the experimental work on *Fomes senex* referred to above.